

The Extraction of Chromium(VI) from Mineral Acid Solutions by Trilaurylamine-Oxide

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Extraction of chromium(VI) from hydrochloric, sulphuric, nitric and orthophosphoric acid solutions by trilaurylamine-oxide (TLAO) in chloroform has been studied. The nature of the extracted chromium(VI) species is established.

HELLER¹ was the first to point out the possibility of using amine-oxides as extracting agents, but was unable to carry out extraction because the self-synthesised compounds of uranyl nitrate with heterocyclic amine-oxides (pyridine-N-oxide and quinoline-N-oxide) were not soluble in organic solvents. Later, several workers²⁻⁷ exploited the potentialities of these reagents as extractants for several metals. We report in this communication the extraction of chromium(VI) by trilaurylamine-oxide (TLAO) from hydrochloric, sulphuric, nitric and orthophosphoric acid solutions.

Experimental

Materials: Chromic acid (E. Merck) was used for preparing chromium(VI) stock solution (0.1M). Chromium-51 in the form of sodium chromate in isotonic saline solution (15 mCi/mg specific activity) and Chlorine-36 as hydrochloric acid solution (5-25 mCi/g specific activity) were obtained from the Isotope Division, Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Bombay. Trilaurylamine-oxide (TLAO) was synthesised by the method described by Davies and Hetzer⁸. Its purity was checked by determining the melting point (m.p. 72°) and molecular weight (cryoscopic method) and by identifying the characteristic ir absorption band for N→O at 965 cm⁻¹. The sample was kept in dry atmosphere in a desiccator over silica gel and in a refrigerator when not in use.

A Single Channel Analyser SC 600 (ECIL, Hyderabad) coupled with a 3" Well type scintillation detector (Nuclear Chicago) was used for γ -activity measurements. β -Activities of the solutions were measured with a liquid G.M. counter.

Procedure: Aqueous solutions (10 ml) containing appropriate concentrations of chromic acid, added tracer and mineral acid were equilibrated for 3-5 min with an equal volume of 0.025M TLAO in chloroform. The two phases were then separated by allowing the mixture to settle for 5 min and centrifuging, if necessary. Equal aliquots (5 ml) of each phase were used to measure the activities from which the distribution coefficient (k_d) was calculated. No volume change in the aqueous and organic phases was observed after equilibration.

Results and Discussion

Bazinger *et al*⁹ reported the extraction of acids by aliphatic amine-oxides as $(R_3N \rightarrow O \dots H \dots O \leftarrow NR_2)^+ A^-$ and as $2 R_3N \rightarrow OH^+ A^-$, respectively from low and high acid media. The formation of such salts has been reported¹⁰ in the case of heterocyclic amine-oxides.

The extraction of chromium(VI) (0.01M) with TLAO/chloroform (0.025M) was studied as a function of aqueous phase concentrations of hydrochloric, sulphuric, nitric and orthophosphoric acid solutions. The k_d values are independent of aqueous phase acidity upto 2M in the case of hydrochloric and sulphuric acid solutions and upto 3M with orthophosphoric acid, beyond which a gradual fall is noticed. On the other hand the extraction is comparatively much less in nitric acid solutions with a gradual fall in k_d with increasing acidity even in the 0.01-0.1M acidity range. The decrease in k_d with increasing acidity in all these systems can be explained [by analogy to the U(VI)-HCl-TOAO system⁹] as due to the decrease in the effective amine-oxide concentration by its bonding to the acid or a competitive extraction process in which the anionic part of the acid preferably gets extracted by the amine-oxide (e.g. $RNOH^+ A^-$). The extraction of chromium(VI) is nearly quantitative from hydrochloric acid medium (% extraction = 98.80 at $\leq 2M$ HCl), as compared with sulphuric acid (% extraction = 99.80 at $\leq 2M$ H₂SO₄) and orthophosphoric acid (% extraction = 99.85 at $\leq 3M$ H₃PO₄) solutions. Addition of NaCl, Na₂SO₄, NaH₂PO₄ and NaNO₃ to aqueous phases resulted in a significant decrease in extraction, the decrease being in the order HNO₃ > HCl > H₂SO₄ $\approx$ H₃PO₄.

The extraction of chromium(VI) as a function of metal concentration [in the concentration range 10⁻⁵-10⁻³ mg/ml of Cr(VI)] with TLAO/chloroform (0.025M) was studied. The log-log plot of the equilibrium chromium(VI) concentration in the aqueous phase vs organic phase at initial aqueous phase acidities of 0.1M and 1.0M with respect to HCl, H₂SO₄ and H₃PO₄ gave straight lines of unit slope, indicating that the extracted chromium(VI) species is monomeric in nature. Under the experimental conditions [max. concentration of Cr(VI) employed is 5.2 $\times$ 10⁻² mg/ml], chromium(VI) exists predo-

TABLE 1—DATA ON THE COMPOSITION OF THE ORGANIC PHASES OBTAINED AFTER EXTRACTION OF CHROMIUM(VI) FROM HCl SOLUTIONS WITH 0.025 M TLAO

Initial aqueous phase (M)		Equilibrium organic phase (M)			Molar ratio organic phase TLAO : Cr(VI) : Cl ₂
[Cr(VI)]	[HCl]	[Cr(VI)]	[Cl ⁻]	[Cl ⁻] (Blank)	
0.03	0.05	0.0250	0.0250	0.0244	1 : 1 : 0.024
0.03	0.10	0.0250	0.0260	0.0244	1 : 1 : 0.024
0.03	0.30	0.0250	0.0295	0.0248	1 : 1 : 0.188
0.03	0.50	0.0250	0.0348	0.0255	1 : 1 : 0.372
0.03	1.00	0.0250	0.0440	0.0260	1 : 1 : 0.720
0.03	2.00	0.0250	0.0450	0.0265	1 : 1 : 0.740
0.04	1.00	0.0250	0.0440	0.0260	1 : 1 : 0.720
0.05	1.00	0.0250	0.0440	0.0260	1 : 1 : 0.720

minantly as monomeric oxyanion¹¹ i.e. HCrO_4^- in the aqueous phase. Therefore the extraction of chromium(VI) as protonated oxyanion can be envisaged. This is in conformity with the observation that other elements which form oxyanions in their highest oxidation states are extracted as protonated oxyanions [e.g. W(VI)^{12} , Mo(VI)^{13} , Re(VII)^{13} and Te(VI)^{14}] by oxygen donor extractants.

number is close to unity (1.05 at 0.1 M HCl). As the concentration of the acid in the aqueous phase is increased, the stoichiometric ratio of the components in the organic phase increases gradually, indicating that different extraction mechanisms are operating probably due to the formation of a mixture of solvated chromium(VI) species. The extract of chromium(VI) (0.03 M) was studied with TLAO/chloroform (0.025 M), using ⁵¹Cr as radiotracer. The concentration of chloride in the organic phase increased with increasing acidity (Table 1) indicating that the extracted chromium(VI) is a mixture of species containing predominantly HCrO_2Cl at higher acidities. The extraction of protonated chromium(VI) species from mineral acid solutions by oxygen donor solvents TBP^{15,16} and TOPO¹⁷ was earlier reported. The existence of such species in aqueous acid systems at high acidities (> 2 M) was also reported by several workers^{18,19}.

The observed Cr : TLAO mole ratio of 2, from sulphuric, nitric and orthophosphoric acid solutions could be explained as arising from the extraction of chromium(VI) species in the form of $2\text{R}_3\text{NO}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{CrO}_4$. On the other hand, the alteration of mole ratio from hydrochloric acid solutions with increasing acidity suggests extraction of a mixture of chromium(VI) species in the form of $\text{R}_3\text{NO}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{CrO}_4$ and/or $\text{R}_3\text{NO}\cdot\text{HCrO}_2\text{Cl}$ at higher acidities (> 0.1 M) and as $\text{R}_3\text{NO}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{CrO}_4$ at lower acidities (< 0.1 M).

Fig. 1. Variation of the distribution coefficient (k_d) for chromium(VI) (5.2×10^{-2} mg/ml) in hydrochloric, sulphuric and orthophosphoric acid solutions as a function of TLAO concentration in chloroform.

The log-log plots of k_d vs (TLAO) (Fig. 1b) from invariable concentrations of sulphuric and orthophosphoric acid solutions (0.1M, 0.5M and 1.0M) gave a square law k_d dependence on the amine-oxide, irrespective of the acid concentration indicating the formation of disolvates. On the other hand, the slope analysis of the distribution data in hydrochloric acid system (Fig. 1a) indicates that the solvation number depends on the concentration of the acid. At low acid concentration the slope of the log k_d vs log (TLAO) plot shows that the solvation

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (M. V. N. M.) is thankful to the University Grants Commission, New Delhi for the award of a Teacher Fellowship under the Faculty Improvement Programme.

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